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User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage.

D2.2 Study of climatic, occupant comfort and energy usage in heritage buildings

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Summary

This deliverable reports the outputs of Task 2.2.

This report presents the factors that must be considered when renovating historical, traditional and heritage buildings for energy efficiency and thermal comfort. Their requirements are different and sometimes more stringent when compared with the renovation of contemporary buildings, which were designed to meet the objectives of energy codes. In the first section, an overview of the situation of heritage buildings regarding energy use and comfort is presented, which shows different energy profiles according to the construction year of the building, but which in general is higher for the segment built between 1920 to 1960, with buildings previous to that time depending on thermal inertia, having a more passive energy behaviour. It is also discussed how a renovation strategy would impact the energy and comfort performance of the building but would also be beneficial from a point of view of sustainability, by taking advantage of the embodied energy of the existing buildings.

The regulatory framework to preserve heritage buildings is presented, which has evolved from purely aesthetic and nationalistic requirements to initiatives for organized preservation, including the regulatory framework for upgrading heritage buildings to reduce energy consumption, achieve thermal comfort and consider the needs of today's occupants. However, the renovation of historic and heritage buildings is a challenging task due to the limitations from heritage protection regulations, that prevent any significant alteration to the architectural and cultural legacy, thus limiting the technological options available to achieve energy efficiency, which can significantly modify the internal energy dynamics of the building if not applied correctly.

The impact of potential solutions for energy, comfort through several options including internal insulation, insulating mortars and window replacements is presented. It is also discussed how the complexity of the renovation process can be addressed by applying a decision-making process to decide on the suitability of solutions for different cases.

The final section of the Deliverable presents the importance of providing accessibility solutions to heritage buildings based on the concept of universal design that must be taken into account when developing renovation planning. This is illustrated through a selection of heritage buildings that have been awarded for their solutions for accessibility, and that are located in demonstration countries.

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**D2.2. Study of climatic, occupant comfort and
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Terms, definitions, and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IEA	International Energy Agency
BPIE	Building Performance Institute of Europe
GBP	Green Building Programme
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Buildings
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers
DHW	Domestic Heat Water
PMV	Predictive Mean Vote
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
RH	Relative Humidity
IEA-SHC	International Energy agency – Solar heating and cooling programme
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
PIR	Polyisocyanurate boards
VIP	Vacuum insulation panels
PCM	Phase Change Materials

1. Introduction: Study criteria

The scope of Deliverable 2.2 is to analyse the aspects involved on the development of an energy renovation plan for historic and heritage buildings. In the context of this deliverable, historic, traditional and heritage buildings are considered synonymous and within the scope of this project, even if they are not necessarily covered in an official heritage listing or preservation order, since the criteria for inclusion can vary from country to country. Historic, traditional and heritage structures are conventionally considered to have been built previous to 1950-1960. The study presented here develops around three main measures: climate conditions, occupant comfort, and energy use. It consists of a literature review of relevant documentation focused on the European countries where the Herit4ages demo-sites are located: Estonia, Italy, Spain, and Portugal. The study includes an overview of the situation of these buildings regarding regulations destined to their preservation, while contrasting it with those regulations that have as focus improvements for energy efficiency to provide a global context on the energy renovation of historic buildings as a subject.

The implications of energy renovation regarding the use of energy at different stages of the construction process and its relevance for historic buildings is also discussed, where relevant concepts such as embodied energy, the building's historic preservation are contemplated. The study also intends to analyse briefly the intersection of conflicting criteria (i.e. energy, comfort, heritage protection) which increases the complexity of the selection of an appropriate solution for every case. Implications regarding climate conditions as well as the actions of the occupants are evaluated, which also make evident the need to implement decision-making within the process.

At the end of the study, case studies awarded for good practices in the addition of accessibility in European heritage buildings are included, to enhance the importance of considering the occupants from a universal-design point of view that adapts these buildings to current requirements, increasing their acceptance.

2. Energy and Technical background for Heritage Buildings

2.1 Historic and heritage buildings in Europe and energy Implications

Reports made on the building stock in Europe, show that historic buildings represent an extensive share since more than 14% of existing buildings were built before 1919, 12% between 1919 and 1945, and around 40% before 1960. Residential buildings constitute 22.7% of those built before 1945, while the share of residential buildings built between 1945–1969 is 26.2% (Hao et al. 2020). Buildings belonging to the period before 1919 (referred to in the text as “traditional buildings”) in Spain and Italy are about 20% and 19% respectively, those after 1945 are 12% and 41% respectively (Özçetin, Atmaca, and Atmaca 2023). An overview of residential buildings according to geographic zones in Europe for the countries relevant for this project (demo site countries) is detailed in Table 1, a graphical representation is shown in Figure 1, with detail for the South (Portugal, Spain and Italy) and the Central-East Zone (Estonia) of Europe.

TABLE 1 SHARE OF HISTORIC BUILDINGS IN EUROPE DURING TWO TIME PERIODS AND RELEVANT COUNTRIES FOR THE PROJECT (ECONOMIDOU 2011)

Region Europe	Pre 1960	1961-1990	1991-2010
South	37%	49%	14%
North-west	42%	39%	19%
Central-East	35%	48%	17%

FIGURE 1. SHARE OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS BY AGE IN TWO ZONES IN EUROPE, WHERE BUILDINGS RELEVANT FOR THIS PROJECT ARE CLASSIFIED (ECONOMIDOU 2011).

According to the European Commission (EC), the energy employed in operating heating, cooling, ventilation, and artificial lighting is responsible for at least 40% of the total building energy consumption, while a large percentage, around 55%, oversees the heating and cooling systems. Buildings are responsible for about 36% of the carbon emissions in 2016 (IEA-International Energy Agency 2012)(ReCO₂ST 2017), while the demand in energy consumption increased about 4% in 2022 (International Energy Agency 2017; 2022).

Regarding the final energy use in historic buildings, those built in the 1960s seem to have a poorer performance than those of earlier decades (Economidou et al. 2011), most likely due to prevalent use of concrete and bricks without significant thermal mass. The energy used for heating for single family homes in older buildings shows a tendency for reduction according to the more recent construction years between 1970s and 1980s, reflecting the gradual introduction of energy codes.

TABLE 2 REDUCTION OF THE FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION WHEN COMPARING THE PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS BUILT BEFORE 1945 WITH THOSE BETWEEN 1980 AND 1989 (kWh/m²/y) (ALEKSANDR ET AL. 2021).

Time period	Italy	Spain	Portugal	Estonia
Approximate proportion of the reduction of the final energy consumption. Comparison between buildings dated before 1945 and those between 1980 and 1989. (kWh/m ² /y).	1% residential, 21% services	31% residential, 20% services	24% residential, 33% services	47% residential, 22% services

Reports also show that the energy consumption in buildings dated from period 1920-1945 present an increased use of final energy compared to those from the 70s and 80s. For example, a significative decrease on space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) of about 40% can be observed between 1945 and 1990 for the existing residential building stock in Spain. For Italy the reduction from older to more recent buildings were minimal for residential buildings during that period. Other values obtained for the countries analysed in this project are shown in Table 2 (Aleksandr et al. 2021). The graphs depicting heating consumption for Portugal and Spain are shown in Figure 2, where the differences between the two countries can be observed.

FIGURE 2. FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION FOR SPACE HEATING AND DHW (kWh/m². y) IN PORTUGAL (LEFT) AND SPAIN (RIGHT), ACCORDING TO CONSTRUCTION YEARS AND TYPE OF BUILDING USAGE (ALEKSANDR ET AL. 2021).

However, building energy performance relies on several factors, such as weather conditions, materials of the building envelope, as well as time of construction. Hence such comparison becomes complex specially when the observation includes buildings pertaining to different construction times and site locations. For instance, in a comparison of existing buildings in the south in Europe, in Portugal, buildings from 1950 to 1970 show a similar performance. In Italy, a reduction is observed between buildings from the 1940s-1960s and those after the 1960s.

A complementary reference would be the average U-value (thermal transmittance), Hao (Hao et al. 2020) reports an average U-value of walls in residential buildings built before 1945 of 1.45 W/m²K, and 1.39 W/m²K for the walls in residential buildings built between 1945–1969. Also, (Economidou et al. 2011), reports historical U-values of walls indicating the insufficient insulation of the building envelope in older buildings, as for instance in 1965 the required value for walls was 1.7 W/m²K and for the roof space 1.4, in 1976 the required value for walls was 1.0 W/m²K and 0.6 for the roof space (Greenage 2015).

While it is not possible to make a definitive statement, the presumption of better performance in the case of older, traditional buildings built pre-1919 might hold certain accuracy. In their case, the constructive methods employed were more adapted to the local weather conditions, indicating a recurring use of passive systems for heating and cooling. As for instance, the use of thermal mass by employing earth or stone to build their

walls, including in some cases the use of deliberate wall perforations to allow natural ventilation, which reduced need of mechanical or active cooling and heating systems (Lidelöw et al. 2019).

Also, in evaluations of acceptability of thermal comfort conditions, it has been reported that occupant's perception of the interior environment is more favourable in traditional buildings compared to modern ones. In the case of thermal sensations in warm weather conditions, the occupants of traditional buildings with natural ventilation declared higher satisfaction than users of modern buildings equipped with air conditioning (Martínez-Molina et al. 2016; Gagliano et al. 2014; Webb 2017). A study performed with residents of buildings dated before 1940, revealed that many of the respondents were satisfied with the thermal conditions in wintertime. In summer, heritage building residents perceived their homes to have excellent performance and show satisfaction with the ventilation levels of the buildings, observed as contrasting with the results obtained in modern buildings from other studies (Wise, Moncaster, and Jones 2022).

2.2 Implications of energy renovation in heritage and historic buildings

The renovation of historic buildings can provide several advantages in terms of energy efficiency since implementing renovation measures would signify a reduction of 28% in terms of primary energy use. By taking advantage of the embodied energy already stored in existing buildings, the use of additional energy required for the construction of new buildings (and the corresponding carbon emissions), would be saved (Lidelöw et al. 2019).

Important savings can be achieved on production processes as well as other aspects such as resource extraction, transportation, manufacture of construction materials and systems. The IEA reports that in 2022, the buildings sector emissions represented around a third of total energy system emissions, which included buildings operations (26%) as well as embodied emissions (7%) associated with the production of materials used for their construction (Bermudez Menendez et al. 2023). Hao's review (Hao et al. 2020), reports that the embodied energy of the construction process could amount to up to 30% of the whole life cycle energy consumption. Authors argue that if demolition was considered, the embodied energy would be discarded. On that regard, it is considered that materials typically employed in older buildings (timber, stone, or clay), would be more easily reabsorbed in nature, allowing a more natural progression of their lifecycle. This is an argument that reinforces the assumption that building renovation would represent lower ecological impacts compared to the construction of new buildings.

Due to the previous statements, it is possible to infer that the energy renovation of historic buildings carries an important sustainable impact. The latter, by considering several perspectives, such as the use of embodied energy (hence production and manufacturing), with the improvement of energy performance and thermal comfort. In addition, the implementation of energy renovation measures would also contribute to safeguard the cultural and historic values of cities, by extending the lifetime of traditional buildings and restoring their use to the requirements of present times. Currently, when it comes to the cultural heritage renovation, the main concern is the preservation of the heritage cultural and historic character, therefore the

implementation of energy renovation measures is highly limited by heritage protection regulations. European countries apply heritage protection measures with different levels of severity, aiming to prevent the alteration of the exterior buildings' appearance. Such measures would limit the potential to modify the building envelope to improve, for instance, the thermal transmittance (U-value) of building elements such as walls, roofs, floors (Caro, Sendra, and Muñoz González 2021).

The protection of historic buildings in Europe had its origins on cultural nationalism, observing an increment of its importance and interest during the nineteenth century. The pertaining rules included strict restrictions to destroy, modify and repair buildings that were previously identified in assembled inventories. Political strategies are presumed to be behind the initial reasons of the creation of the preservation directives, among the base criteria were internal and external threats or the promotion and reinforcement of national identity (Thatcher 2018a; 2018b). Other non-nationalistic aims arose afterwards, which were based on commercialization incentives, such as the growth of tourism and the heritage industry, as well as the regeneration of historic urban landscapes (Thatcher 2018a). In recent years, the protection of historic buildings has been increasingly challenged by climate change concerns. Reducing the use of fossil fuels for energy production would be a long-term goal for heritage buildings, leading to the implementation of policies to reduce overall energy consumption derived from human activities (Serrano Lanzarote et al. 2020).

The heritage building sector seems to agree that the renovation of historical buildings is a compromise between heritage protection and the magnitude of improvements to energy and comfort. A suggested approach to achieve both goals, includes to carefully analyse the type and degree of interventions to be implemented on the building. Authors (Şahin et al. 2015) report the use of active and passive retrofit measures implemented specifically in heritage buildings to achieve energy savings of 20-40%. They concluded that 20% savings could be reached without disturbing heritage value while 40% was achievable but an unlikely target. The Review presented by Lidelow (Lidelöw et al. 2019), reports that the most common interventions range from minor to moderate retrofitting, consisting of single or multiple measures, rather than measures applied to the entire building (Lidelöw et al. 2019). In contrast, according to the Building Performance Institute of Europe (BPIE), minor and moderate degree of energy saving interventions might be performed in historic buildings to achieve the 2050 energy and CO₂ target reductions. The report indicates that up to 30% reductions on the final energy demand can be achieved by the implementation of minor interventions, moderate interventions would represent 30-60%, while deep interventions would be 60-90%, and nZEB would enable over 90% reductions (Özçetin, Atmaca, and Atmaca 2023). The main concerns nowadays focus on determining the magnitude and the kind of measures that can be implemented without damaging the building's integrity and historic significance.

3. Requirements of energy use and occupant's comfort

3.1 Building directives in Europe for energy efficiency

Several initiatives have been taken by the EU to promote energy efficiency in buildings. The Green Building Programme (GBP) is an initiative that promotes the improvement of energy efficiency as well as the use of renewable systems in non-residential buildings (*DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 2010*). The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, Directive 2002/91/EC), and its recast in 2010 (EPBD recast, Directive 2010/31/EC) encourages the implementation of nearly zero energy buildings (NZEBs) as the target for new constructions from 2018 onwards (*DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/844 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 30 May 2018 2018*). Since their creation, there has been an increased interest about the need to reduce energy consumption in heritage buildings (Mazzarella 2015).

Other initiatives, such as the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) (*DIRECTIVE (EU) 2023/1791 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 13 September 2023 2023*) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) (*DIRECTIVE (EU) 2023/2413 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 18 October 2023 2023*) also aim to promote improvements in the energy performance of the European buildings. The revised directive aims to increase the rate of renovation, particularly for the worst-performing non-residential buildings in each country by 2030, to reach a goal of 26% building renovations by 2033, while the achievement of improved environmental quality is also encouraged.

However, as explained in the previous section, the protection to the cultural character and heritage value of historical buildings signifies a limiting factor to the improvement of their energy performance. The EPBD 2010 recast (*DIRECTIVE 2010/31/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 May 2010 2010*), concedes the possibility of exception in the case of historic buildings, stating: “*Members might decide not to apply the requirement in the case of buildings officially protected because of their historical merit, as compliance with certain minimum energy performance requirements would unacceptably alter their character or appearance*”. However, as mentioned by (Webb 2017), the perspectives about the importance of retrofit activities on historic buildings have been increasingly changed, and nowadays retrofitting is considered as a mean of protection, as it could be useful to improve the buildings current situation for reuse or adaptation. In correspondence with that, the European Directive 2018(*DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/844 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 30 May 2018 2018*), encourages the testing of new solutions for improving the energy performance of historical buildings, if the cultural heritage is safeguarded: “*research into, and the testing of, new solutions for improving the energy performance of historical buildings and sites should be encouraged, while also safeguarding and preserving cultural heritage*”. The last revision declares the need to allow for improvement in energy performance without altering their technical character and appearance (EPRS_BRI (2022) 698901_EN) (Dulian 2024).

While the most recent directives encourage the use of renovation strategies, they also demand the implementation of a meticulous process to find the balance between allowed interventions and potential

energy improvements as a result. An exhaustive evaluation of the building’s historic and physical characteristics should be performed first, as in many cases, their inherent features (e.g. thermal mass, passive ventilation), would contribute to the achievement of an adequate energy performance.

3.2 Requirements for energy and comfort in buildings in Europe

In Europe, several efforts have been carried-out in recent years to investigate the most adequate strategies and technologies to improve energy and comfort in historic buildings. However, it is still not possible to reach conclusive agreements leading to the implementation of comprehensive guidelines, since the outcomes resulting from those initiatives are not yet able to deeply address the requirements of historic buildings. The latter might be due to the difficulties to incorporate the many disparities between countries, building typologies, architectural styles, historic legacies, with aspects related to energy performance, such as climate conditions and so on. Hence, in many cases, the regulatory framework for the design of new energy efficient buildings and the corresponding transition of existing buildings, would be still pertinent for the purposes of energy renovation in historic buildings. Regarding regional initiatives, efforts have also been made to develop local regulatory frameworks in certain European countries with the objective of performing an adaptation to local requirements and conditions.

In the case of Italy, which counts with one of the highest proportions of heritage buildings in Europe, in their criteria, the importance of building conservation precedes that of achieving energy improvements. Hence, concepts such as minimal interventions and reversibility are mentioned on their studies, also enhancing the importance of counting with experts on both fields (building energy and conservation) (de Santoli 2015). References to the most relevant standards and regulations usually applied in Europe are shown in Table 3, which indicate the requirements for new and existing buildings to assess energy and comfort. The most relevant norms for assessing thermal comfort and air quality in buildings are included here, while additional ones can be consulted in (Ochoa et al. 2020; Hartman et al. 2013).

TABLE 3 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK ON ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND COMFORT APPLICABLE TO EXISTING AND NEW BUILDINGS IN EUROPE

Norm	Date	Description
ISO 7726	1998	Ergonomics of the thermal environment - Instruments for measuring physical quantities
ISO 7730	2005	Prediction of thermal sensation of a group of people, based on Fanger’s Predicted Mean Vote (PMV).
EN 15251	2007	Specifies indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting, and acoustics. There is need for specifying environmental criteria for design, energy calculations, performance, and operation of buildings.
Directive 2008/50/EC	2008	Ambien air quality and cleaner air for Europe.
WHO guidelines	2009	Indoor air quality: dampness and mould.

EN 12464-1	2011	Lighting Standard specifies lighting requirements for people in indoor workplaces. It covers all indoor working areas including but not limited to offices, industry, healthcare, retail, restaurants, hotels, museums, libraries, schools, and car parks.
ISO 17772-1	2017	International. Established standards for thermal comfort Energy Performance of buildings – Indoor environmental quality – Part 1 – Indoor environmental input parameters for the design and assessment of energy performance of buildings.
ASHRAE 55	2017, Rev. 2023	International. Thermal environmental conditions for human occupancy, defines conditions that are being considered satisfactory for a specific percentage of users.

While the above-mentioned norms are generally applied in Europe, regional regulations are also implemented in few countries, while in others, those are missing or are not set as imperative. While the existence of local regulation would address the specific needs of certain EU countries, it is also argued that the requirements across countries present several inconsistencies (as an example shown in Table 4). Hence, it is believed that the implementation of the European Standards should ensure an adequate interior environment, and that building occupants as well as the HVAC industry would benefit from a homogeneous normative framework across the EU countries (Brelj 2013).

TABLE 4 THERMAL AND ACOUSTIC COMFORT REQUIREMENTS IN EU AGAINST REGIONAL REGULATIONS (BRELIH 2023).

Aspect	European Regulation	Regional Regulations
Indoor air temperature	EN15251:2007. The recommended values in are 20 °C and 26 °C for winter and summer respectively.	Limits vary: 25 to 28 °C in summer, 15 to 21 °C in winter.
Air humidity	Limits are constantly at 30% (lower) and 70% (higher) at national and European level regulations.	70% relative humidity in summer and 30% relative humidity in winter.
Requirements for noise	Compared to EN 15251, in the classrooms and offices they are set to 35 dB, which is exceeded in the regulations of several countries, the noise limits are set to high.	For bedrooms in dwellings is 28 dB, lower limits for classrooms are 28 to 40 decibels, while in offices are 33 to 45 decibels.

3.3 The development of a regulatory framework for heritage and historic buildings in Europe

The creation of standards and guidelines applicable to the energy renovation on historic buildings would require that specific aspects for their performance would be considered. The thermal behaviour in a building depends on the interaction between thermal inertia, insulation, and ventilation strategies. Therefore, aspects related to the physical condition of the building envelope might be the most relevant to consider in an initial evaluation. Those would include hygrothermal behaviour, interior insulation, the improvement of the U-value, air tightness and windows retrofit (upgrade from single glazing to double glazing or triple glazing). In historic and traditional buildings, cracking, shrinking of wood or plaster materials could occur over time due to building settlement, creating gaps in the building envelope allowing heat loss and air leakages. Passive ventilation strategies common in many traditional buildings should be taken advantage of to keep a stable

RH value. Since relative humidity (RH) is an important indicator for mould prevention or decay, a low RH could cause cracks in certain materials (Webb 2017; Nair, Verde, and Olofsson 2022). Energy audits are useful to identify such problems and make renovation plans for their repair and identification of suitable solutions, considering the heritage protection applied to every case. For example, the application of external insulation is frequently limited by building protection regulations, hence internal insulation is often employed instead.

Since the last few decades, several initiatives have been created to address the energy renovation of historic buildings, the most relevant ones are listed in Table 5 (Vieites, Vassileva, and Arias 2015). Committees and boards with specific tasks missions, have as an objective to develop methods, strategies, and guidelines that contribute to accomplish the special requirements of heritage buildings, by considering them as an exceptional category. Their activities include the characterisation of materials, the evaluation and improvement of processes, and methodologies that could balance energy intervention strategies together with the conservation of their historical and cultural value.

TABLE 5 EUROPEAN INITIATIVES FOR THE CREATION OF METHODS, STRATEGIES, AND GUIDELINES FOR ENERGY RENOVATION IN HISTORIC BUILDINGS.

Project	Description
Initiative: Energy Efficient Buildings (new and existing)	
EuroACE (1998)	European Alliance of Companies for Energy Efficiency in Buildings. EuroACE 2022 Renovation of historic, heritage, and protected buildings: Recommendations & case studies
Build UP (2009)	European reference portal for energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings.
ReCO2st (2017)	Residential Retrofit assessment platform and demonstrations for near zero energy and CO ₂ emissions with optimum cost, health, comfort, and environmental quality. Best Practice Handbook.
Initiative: Historic Buildings	
NEW4OLD (2010)	Evaluates the integration of renewable energy technologies in heritage buildings. Aimed to reduction of the energy demand for HVAC. Other measures insulation of the building envelope (walls and roof), energy efficient luminaires, mechanical ventilation system and renewable energy technologies.
EFFESUS (2016)	Energy efficiency of European historic urban districts, considering buildings dated before 1945, but not earmarked for heritage protection. Type of interventions included PV and energy storage at district level, building envelope insulating solutions. Indoor climate control systems, and secondary glazing.
3ENCULT (2014)	Focused on the conservation of historic buildings with the use of innovative technologies and materials with the objective of protecting the heritage features. Technologies included interior insulation, heritage compatible windows, lighting, solar integration of PV cells and biomass boilers, as well as a wireless monitoring system.
RESSEEPE (2013)	Present innovative retrofit technologies to achieve at least 50% reduction on energy consumption. Technologies applied to the building envelope include, ventilated facades, installation of insulating panels, PV integration and thermal collectors, thermal storage and PCM.
Short Guide, Historic Scotland (2014)	Fabric Improvement for energy efficiency in traditional buildings (www.historic-scotland.gov.uk)
RIBuild (2015)	Robust Internal Thermal Insulation of Historic buildings

IEA-SHC TASK 59 (2017)	Renovating Historic Buildings Towards Zero Energy. The IEA-SHC-Task 59 recommendations for ‘best practices’, that can be generic for new/existing/historic buildings. Renovation Strategies.
European Commission (2018)	European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage
Build UP Overview (2019)	Overview, Energy efficiency in historic buildings: A state of the Art

For instance, the IEA-SHC Task 59 recommends a minimum level of assessment, to fulfil requirements on Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), and to avoid measures that risk moisture problems indoors. The task also suggests a ‘gatekeeper’ procedure to select the level of intervention, which requires to identify a long and a short list (audits to identify what is required from energy performance point of view, and what is feasible from a heritage protection, technical or economic point of view). On the IEA-SHC Task 59 Handbook, as well as the ‘Fact Sheet Guidelines’ a list of relevant norms and standards can be consulted (Buda and Brostrom 2020; Leijonhufvud 2021). For the assessment and implementation of energy efficient solutions in historic buildings, guidelines and case studies can be consulted (Buda, Herrera, and Pfluger 2021; Scotland 2018).

As a result of those initiatives, several methods and strategies have been developed, including an exploratory set of regulations (Table 6), that oversee the performance of solutions and strategies for the building heritage category. In Europe, the standard EN 16883, refers to the conservation of the cultural heritage, provides guidelines to improve the energy performance of historic buildings. Other international standards, such as those proposed by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) are also intended to rehabilitate historic buildings to achieve energy efficiency, while preserving the historical character of the building. A set of guidelines address issues such as energy conservation, commissioning processes, existing HVAC systems, or cases such as commercial buildings or owners and managers (Phoenix 2015; Webb 2017).

TABLE 6 EUROPEAN AND INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS AND NORMS APPLICABLE TO THE ENERGY RENOVATION OF HISTORIC BUILDINGS.

Standard	Date	Description
EN 16883	2017	Conservation of cultural heritage – guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings.
EN 16893	2018	For preventive conservation of cultural heritage – specifications for location, construction and modification of buildings or room for the storage of heritage collections.
ASHRAE 0.2P	2013	The commissioning process for Existing Systems and Assemblies
ASHRAE 1.2P	2015	The commissioning process for existing HVAC&R Systems
ASHRAE 34P	2019	Provides guidance to rehabilitate and restore historic buildings and structures to achieve energy efficiency without compromising historical preservation.

As mentioned previously in this section, some EU countries have also advanced on the development of a regulatory framework for assessing the energy and comfort performance which considers specific local requirements or conditions. Those related to the demo countries of this project are shown in Table 7 (Heiskanen, Matschoss, and Kuusi 2014; Kranzl et al. 2014; Direcao Geral de Energia e Geologia 2014; de Santoli 2015; Schimschar, Surmeli, and Hermelink 2013).

TABLE 7 DIRECTIVES AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK ON ENERGY AND COMFORT PARAMETERS APPLICABLE TO EXISTING AND HISTORIC BUILDINGS IN RELEVANT COUNTRIES FOR THIS PROJECT.

Norm/regulation	Details	Reference
Spain		
CTE DB HE-2013	Sets the minimum mandatory requirements according to tabulated values of energy need (heating and cooling) and primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² year) for new residential buildings or building enlargements	Entranze Project
DB HE 2006 up to BOE 15/06/2022	Regarding existing buildings, the minimum requirement is fixed according to a reference building according to thermal comfort, location, summer and winter use.	National plan for increasing the number of nZEBs in Spain
Law 8/2013	On urban rehabilitation, regeneration, and renovation	
Italy		
Legislative Decree No 192 of 2005	New Buildings	
Legislative Decree No 192 of 2005 a	Existing Buildings for energy performance according to climate zone.	
AiCARR guidelines 2014	Energy efficiency in Historic Buildings	Santoli 2015 https://www.aicarr.org/
Portugal		
Decree Law No 118/2013 of 20 August 2013	Policies and measures for the promotion of existing buildings undergoing major renovation being transformed to nearly zero energy buildings	Direcao Geral de Energia e Geologia. National plan for increasing the number of nearly zero-energy buildings, Portugal
Law No 58/2013 of 20 August 2013		
Estonia		
	Policies and measures for the promotion of existing buildings undergoing major renovation being transformed to nearly zero-energy buildings.	Ecofys. National plan for increasing the number of nearly zero energy buildings, Estonia.

4. The energy and comfort impact of potential solutions

4.1 Energy renovation measures typically applied to heritage and historic buildings

Active and passive strategies can be implemented as renovation solutions to achieve energy efficient heritage buildings. With the use of passive solutions, the building's energy consumption can be reduced by taking advantage of the natural performance of the building in interaction with the outdoor conditions. Active measures involve the upgrading of HVAC systems, implementation of efficient lighting equipment, appliances and controls, the usage of renewable energy sources and systems for an efficient distribution of energy. Renovation measures applied to the building may include interventions to the building envelope, windows, energy systems upgrades, as well as renewable systems integration. Those applied to the building envelope may include the elimination of thermal bridges, air tightness control, and external or internal insulation (Hao et al. 2020). However, as mentioned in the previous sections, the interventions on historic buildings would be limited by heritage protection regulations relevant to the countries where the building is located. Therefore, internal insulation is the most common intervention in heritage buildings since use of external insulation or external elements in windows such as shading devices would be conditioned by local heritage protection regulations.

Walls and roof usually account for more than 50% of heat losses (Trois et al. 2011), therefore an insulation replacement would considerably improve the occupant's thermal comfort and the buildings energy performance. So-called "breathable" materials are recommended for the walls to control the moisture content. Aerogel and polyisocyanurate boards (PIR) are innovative materials that have shown reductions on U-value up to 70% and 61% respectively. Considering the principles of reversibility which are often applied to historic building renovations, some materials are not recommended due to the difficulties to remove their residues, while partial insulation of walls represents an alternative, as energy savings above 30% could be achieved (Nair, Verde, and Olofsson 2022). Wall insulation with a thickness between 150-120mm is an improved and cost optimal solution in warm climate conditions (Tadeu et al. 2015). Floor insulation can be very effective, achieving 30% improvements on the U-value. In some cases the U-value could be adjusted from a usual 3.5 W/m²K to around 0.6 W/m²K for basement floors (Trois et al. 2011). Heat losses through floors can represent 10% of total heat loss in a building. A 10 cm insulation would reduce the losses by 60%. However, it is recommended to implement such measure only in significantly colder areas (Hartman et al. 2013).

Interventions to the building envelope would also include the sealing of window frames, or junctions of walls, floor, and ceiling to prevent heat losses due to air leakages. These can be done using silicone or wool compression materials and could reduce air leakages by 30-55%. Windows usually account for about 10-20% of heat losses. A typical timber frame with single glazing could have a U-value of 5.5 W/m²K, but in average the thermal transmittance could go from 0.7 and 1.5 W/m²K. Improvements including adding internal shutters can lower the value to 2.2 W/m²K. Upgrading from double or triple glazing leads to U-values lower

than 2.2 W/m²K. The thermal transmittance of argon-filled double glazing is on average 1.1 W/m²K, and triple glazing can be 0.7 W/m²K (Troï et al. 2011; Troï and Bastian 2015; D’Agostino, Cuniberti, and Bertoldi 2017).

Active renovation measures include the application (either new or as a system upgrade) of high-performance energy systems such as HVAC solutions that show a primary energy consumption reduction between 20% and 65%. Control automation can also be used to regulate the energy demand/supply. It includes control systems for daylight, presence and motion, as well as to monitor appliances, ventilation, heating, and lighting (Martínez-Molina et al. 2016; D’Agostino, Cuniberti, and Bertoldi 2017).

4.2 The challenges involved on the energy renovation of heritage and historic buildings

It is worth mentioning that the implementation of renovation strategies in existing buildings must be the result of integrated evaluations since the implementation of individual solutions might imply some risks. For instance, the addition of internal insulation with low or no porosity may minimize the favourable effects of thermal mass and natural ventilation strategies. Internal insulation might signify changes on hygrothermal performance and boundary conditions on the wall, which can increase the potential risk of overheating in retrofitted historic buildings. In addition, a tight draught-proof layer might cause increased moisture due to poor air ventilation (Hao et al. 2020; Özçetin, Atmaca, and Atmaca 2023; Nair, Verde, and Olofsson 2022).

In the case of cooling dominated climates, one of the most typical decisions to take refers to the feasibility of applying a retrofitting solution to the exterior façade. The preservation of the architectural or heritage values would be one important reason to defer this solution, as well as the possible side effects due to the existence of thermal inertia, as it could result in overheating during summertime or in prevailing sunny locations (Corrêa et al. 2020). More on this topic is explored in Table 8, where the implications of implementing energy renovation criteria is analysed. Three relevant criteria are considered in this examination: air tightness, thermal insulation, and window replacement, presenting the challenges, solutions, connection with outdoor conditions and heritage preservation. The intention of this exercise is to visualize the interconnection of different criteria, and how they often constitute a conglomerate of conflicting goals and effects.

TABLE 8 ANALYSIS OF CHALLENGES, SOLUTIONS, AND IMPLICATIONS OF THEIR IMPLEMENTATION IN HISTORIC BUILDINGS OF THREE RELEVANT ENERGY RENOVATION CRITERIA.

Goal: Improve thermal conditions indoors		
Renovation criteria applied for the building envelope		
1-Air tightness to prevent thermal losses	2-Thermal Insulation	3-Window replacement
Characteristic performance in traditional and historical buildings		
Historic buildings rely on breathable envelopes and small openings as form of passive ventilation. Cracks on the building envelope may occur caused by the settlement of the construction through time, creating air leaks that	Numerous old buildings are characterized by strong thermal inertia (high mass and thickness).	Window elements in old buildings might be energy inefficient in their original construction (single glazing), or due to natural deterioration.

would result on thermal losses through ceiling, walls, floor, and windows.		
Implications for climate conditions		
<p>Challenge: air tightness is a crucial building renovation strategy for the improvement of energy performance. However, its implementation would displace the original bioclimatic approach for natural ventilation typically employed in traditional buildings.</p> <p>In regions with mediterranean climate (or warm summer months), natural ventilation contributes to energy efficiency with high thermal inertia via night-time cooling. In colder climates, the utilization of natural ventilation systems may increase heat losses and energy costs. In temperate climates, it contributes to heat rejection, economic savings, and better thermal comfort.</p> <p>Solution: When improving the thermal insulation or airtightness of the building, natural ventilation would be insufficient leading to the inclusion of active or mechanical systems (Rieser 2021).</p>	<p>Challenge: Mediterranean climates present a significant range of daily temperatures. Thermal inertia contributes to maintain low temperature oscillations in the interior in summertime but present poor thermal performance in winter due to lack of thermal insulation.</p> <p>Solution: A passive solution would be to increase the thermal resistance of facades to ensure indoor temperatures within a comfortable range in wintertime. The thermal insulation of the building envelope can be external, in the cavity of double walls, or internally applied (Correa 2020). An active solution could be to provide space heating (continuous or intermittent), or local heating (localized heating sources) (Della Torre 2016).</p> <p>Constrains: Internal thermal insulation would be more suitable for historic buildings due to the restrictions for external appearance modifications (RIBuild 2014). Active heating solutions would require certain modifications to the building.</p>	<p>Challenge: The window performance is important to control heat loss and solar gains in summertime. However, solar admission might be desirable or undesirable depending on the location and/or time of the year.</p> <p>Solution: For heat loss control, the use of triple glazing is advisable for cold/temperate climates, namely most of Europe except the Mediterranean region. Low-e glazing would be more suitable for south-west coastal Atlantic climates. For the north of Europe, triple glazing with an additional single pane, quadruple glazing or vacuum glazing would be more suitable. For the control of the solar admission, to avoid visual alteration of the exterior façade, the use of integrated shading devices is recommended, which are placed in a casement or in the window air gap (Troi 2015).</p>

4.3 Decision making process to find the most suitable strategies and solutions for renovation of heritage and historic buildings

The impact of the measures to improve energy performance in heritage buildings should be therefore assessed from an energy and heritage conservation perspective. The EN 16883 (Conservation of Cultural Heritage - Guidelines for Improving the Energy Performance of Historic Buildings) includes a decision-making procedure that considers seven steps, among them the identification of alternatives and the assessment of solutions and strategies leading to energy savings, comfort, feasibility, and reversibility.

Simpler or more comprehensive approaches for decision making process can be found on (Leijonhufvud 2021; Corrêa et al. 2020; Buda, Herrera, and Pfluger 2021), which use discriminating questions to assist on the achievement of the most adequate approach and solution. In order to provide an example, Figure 3 shows the flow chart to assist on the decision-making process to find the most adequate thermal insulation strategy of buildings pre-1960, according to (Corrêa et al. 2020).

FIGURE 3. SCHEMATIC APPROACH TO ASSIST ON THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS OF THERMAL INSULATION STRATEGIES, CORREA ET AL 2020.

4.4 Representation of energy renovation solutions and their impact on energy and comfort

From a technical perspective, a well-documented database of existing solutions should be assembled, where their impact is assessed regarding the most relevant performance aspects:

- a) Impact on heating energy demand
- b) Impact on cooling energy demand
- c) Impact on improving indoor air quality.
- d) Impact on improving indoor thermal comfort.
- e) Construction feasibility in heritage buildings

Table 9 presents a similar approach used in EU projects, where innovative renovation solutions applicable to heritage buildings are classified according to their impact on heating, cooling, thermal comfort, or air quality. A brief description of five solutions selected from those included in the table is provided afterwards.

TABLE 9 REVIEW OF SOLUTIONS FOR HERITAGE BUILDINGS AND THEIR IMPACT ON ENERGY AND COMFORT (TROI ET AL. 2016; 2011).

	Technology	Project Reference	Performance aspect (see text)				
			a	b	c	d	e
Passive Methods							
1	Vacuum insulation panels (VIP)	ReCO2st 2017	x				
2	Aerogel insulation	EFFESUS 2017	x			x	x
3	Insulation Mortar	EFFESUS 2017	x			x	x
4	Phase change materials (PCM)	3ENCULT 2010	x			x	
5	Radiant reflective coatings	EFFESUS 2017		x		x	
6	Roof Insulation	3ENCULT 2010, EFFESUS 2017	x			x	x
7	Vapour Barriers	3ENCULT 2010			x		x
8	Hygroscopic insulation	3ENCULT 2010			x		x
9	Secondary glazing	3ENCULT 2010	x			x	x
10	Window replacement	3ENCULT 2010, EFFESUS 2017	x			x	x
11	Integrated shading systems	3ENCULT 2010		x		x	
Active Methods							
12	Control systems (thermal, lighting)	EFFESUS 2017	x	x	x	x	
13	High efficiency HVAC systems	3ENCULT 2010, EFFESUS 2017	x	x	x	x	
14	Integrated PV modules	3ENCULT 2010	x	x		x	

Selected solutions:

1. *VIP panels*. Improved thermal comfort by reducing heat gains can be achieved with VIP panels due to the vacuum layer that allows a product with considerable reductions in its thickness, making it a candidate for internal insulation as it takes away less space. If the VIPs are installed in the inner side of external walls, complementary insulation works are needed on the floor and ceiling to prevent risk of condensation and mould growth. Any thermal bridges are accentuated due to the small thickness of the insulation, requiring very flush installation. Its use as external insulation can change the building appearance, becoming an issue in listed buildings.

2. *Aerogel insulation.* Spacefill is a unique, thin, highly efficient insulation for use in historic buildings. High performance insulation is inserted into an existing cavity through the empty space between the masonry and wall plaster finish. Its advantage also lies on its simplicity and minimal requirements for redecoration. However, it can only be used in buildings with cavity walls.
3. *Insulation mortar.* Isocal is an insulating render, to be used on masonry on heritage buildings, it uses a specific quality of lime that allows the render to be used in interior and exterior, as it shows sufficient resistance versus mechanical and environmental elements. The materials provide a high vapour transmission rate and is compatible with historic mineral substrates. A finish material should be applied over the substance to provide additional protection and improve the impact strength.
4. *Radiant reflective coatings.* Usually installed on the exterior wall or the roof, this coating designed with high infrared reflection, reduces the amount of solar heat absorbed by the envelope to improve its performance and reduce the cooling needs in the building. It is suitable for historic buildings preferably in warmer climates since it is durable, aesthetically acceptable, reversible, and non-intrusive.
5. *Window replacement.* An innovative technology for energy efficient windows suitable for historic buildings is presented in the European project Effesus (Troi et al. 2016) where different prototypes are analysed. The improvement criteria included: thermal performance, visual thermal transmittance and G-value, moisture analysis. Other additional criteria such as reversibility, durability, maintenance, cost effectiveness was considered during the design. Four prototypes were tested, they consider the use of ‘thermal shades’ installed in the air gap between the glass layers; a second one includes the use of adhesive plastic films with low-emissivity properties that can be added to existing glass. A ‘multi-layered glazing’ uses insulated glazing units that include thin glass planes to provide high insulation levels in a light weight and narrow unit. The ‘air sandwich’ integrates five transparent thin plastic layers glued to original panes to increase thermal resistance and reduce the radiation heat exchange for better thermal performance. The ‘supply air window’ allows fresh air to flow from outside to inside through a designed gap between two panes of glazing in a convection/conduction process, increasing the performance of the window.

4.5 Climate, user profile and occupancy implications for building typologies.

Five different building typologies are studied in this project: educational (classroom), residential building (apartment), working environment (an open-space office), lodging (hotel room) and a former church building used as a heritage lab, with the latter having irregular occupancy due to its research nature. Table 10 includes an overview of different conditions that influence the energy and comfort performance in the demo sites having regular occupancy in this project (including aspects related to climate, user profile, use times). Some observations are then included regarding the implications that such conditions may have on the energy and comfort strategy to be implemented in each building type.

TABLE 10 OVERVIEW OF CLIMATIC AND OCCUPANCY CONDITIONS OF DEMO SITES ANALYSED IN THIS PROJECT

Country / Building typology	Koppen Climate Classification	Generic Profile at demo site: Age range and Occupancy patterns	Implications for energy and comfort
Tartu, Estonia (EE) Office	Dfb D : continental zone north latitude	Staff/Employees, Age: 18-40, Occupancy: Mon-Fri. 09-17h	Working environments are probably the most researched building typology. Comfort temperatures are often mis-calculated by

	warm humid summer climate. Cool summer. At least one month colder than -3°C, f=wet/humid, b=mild summer	Offices show regular occupancy patterns. It can be challenging to develop a single thermal comfort strategy in open-space offices to satisfy all the occupants.	disregarding adaptation or preferences of occupants. In a review of naturally ventilated offices analysed in several countries, comfort temperature was found as low as 17.6 °C and as high as 31.2 °C (Lamsal, Bajracharya, and Rijal 2023). Air-conditioned spaces show a narrow range (22°C to 28°C)(Arsad et al. 2023), thermostat levels are often set to 20°C and 26°C for winter/summer. There is also gender-based difference in thermal preferences. Women seem to be more dissatisfied with thermal environment than men, perceiving colder offices than men in summer (Parkinson et al. 2021).
Aguilar de Campoo, Spain (ES) Hotel	Csb Cool Dry Mediterranean Climate, Warm Temperate, dry, warm summers, the coldest month is warmer than -3°C but colder than +18°C annual temperature range and few extremes of temperature s= dry summer season, b=mild summer	Guest/Worker, Age: 0-89, Occupancy Mon-Fri and weekend: 16h, 00-8am, 15-18pm, 18-23pm. Very irregular occupancy patterns depending on holidays, weekends and tourist seasons.	Hotels require high levels of thermal comfort, while their users are large energy consumers as they are not aware of their consumption. In a research evaluation with visitors from different regions including Europe and Asia, guests preferences for indoor temperatures are slightly higher (2°C) in summer than in winter, between 22°C and 23.5°C in winter and between 24°C and 26°C in summer (Takii, Iba, and Hokoi 2023).
Bologna, Italy (IT) University Classroom	Cfa Humid subtropical climate Temperate/Mid-latitude Humid (C). Coldest month between 0°C and 18°C. Mean temperature in warmest month 22°C or higher f=humid, a=hot summer	University Student/University Teacher, Age: 18-50. Occupancy: Mon-Fri 9am-19pm. Varying occupant numbers during short term periods, maximum of around 60 people at once. The area is unoccupied during weekends and a few weeks in summer and wintertime. Some audio-visual equipment in use.	Provide an adequate thermal environment indoors in wintertime, as well as an adequate ventilation due to high occupancy. In adaptive thermal comfort environments people accept higher temperatures (de Dear and Brager 1998). In air-conditioned classrooms in the winter season, students feel comfortable at lower temperatures so heating system temperature can be set lower (Singh et al. 2019). Usually educational buildings show a wider range of tolerance for thermal comfort (15°C to 32°C)(Arsad et al. 2023).
Funchal, Madeira Portugal (PT) Residential Apartment Building	Cfb temperate oceanic climate Cool summers and mild winters with a narrow annual temperature range and few extremes f=humid, b=mild summer	Long-term tenants Age 40-60, Occupancy Mon-Fri:16h, 8am-9am, 18pm-24pm, Weekend: 00-24pm. On weekdays, mostly unoccupied during the day, irregular occupancy during weekends.	A temperate climate with mild winters and few extreme temperatures. An adequate thermal environment in winter days and during cool evenings/nights needs to be provided. In residential buildings, in temperate climates, the mean comfort temperature was found 22.9°C (Aqilah, Rijal, and Zaki 2022). A wide range preferences for indoor temperature is also reported in residential buildings (17°C to 33°C) (Arsad et al. 2023).

As it can be observed in Table 10 regarding thermal comfort in different building typologies, most of the observations indicate that adaptation levels and occupants' preferences are often disregarded as an important factor when comfort levels are established in the room/buildings. A difference of one or two degrees on a thermostat set-point temperature can signify an increased energy use due to over or underestimation of comfort levels accepted or preferred by occupants. There are also gender and age implications in user preferences for indoor temperatures. An energy renovation in heritage buildings would have as a goal to increase their thermal performance, primarily using passive strategies and solutions as mentioned in Section 4.4. Passive strategies would reduce the use of active solutions, or in some cases could even be avoided as their installation usually implies the use of intrusive methods that require modifications to the building fabric.

It is worth mentioning that the church building studied in this project currently has no regular occupancy activities as it is mainly used as a Heritage Laboratory to test and develop different methods and technologies. However, heritage buildings of such typology (chapels, church buildings with regular usage), represent very challenging cases from an energy efficiency point of view. They are characterized by considerable large single volumes that require significant energy to maintain an adequate thermal environment indoors. Usually, they are made of solid materials (rock) and thick walls, that provides them with high thermal mass. However, due to their historic and architectural relevance, it is not rare that both the interior and exterior of the building is protected against retrofitting interventions. A passive solution would be to improve the thermal insulation of the building envelope to reduce the use of heating and cooling equipment. However, the improvement of interior thermal conditions by installing internal insulation might be narrow in such cases. Active systems could be employed to heat the space, in two possible modes, space heating (continuous or intermittent), or local heating (localized heating sources). However, beside ensuring an adequate thermal environment indoors for the occupants' satisfaction, the conservation of historic fabric and artefacts (frescoes, textiles, etc.), should also be considered as part of the renovation strategy. It is known that fluctuations in temperature and humidity can cause objects to expand and contract which might affect the heritage objects/materials or other buildings components. Therefore, the renovation strategy should ensure stable temperature levels indoors, with the use of passive/active solutions. One example of such interventions can be found the solution achieved in the Basilica di Collemaggio in Italy, where a localized heating solution using a radiant system installed on the benches was employed in combination with water-to-water ground source heat pumps (Aste et al. 2016).

5. Study of accessibility in heritage and historic buildings in Europe, good practices, and awards

Accessibility and inclusiveness must be considered when planning the renovation of heritage buildings as a reflection of the social dynamics and behaviours of contemporary populations and their longer life expectancies. Many heritage buildings in their original condition present significant barriers for accessibility (e.g. long flights of stairs, uneven surfaces, dimly lit spaces), since such concept was not considered in their original planning due to the design priorities and available technologies when they were built.

The following tables present exemplary interventions in significant heritage buildings located in the same countries and usages as the pilots, and that can be used as references. The analysis presents their accessibility and inclusiveness solutions, which required significant planning for ergonomic suitability.

5.1 Hotels, Spain

BARCELONA, SPAIN, C. dels Lledó, 7, Ciutat Vella, 08002	
Building function/typology	Mercer Hotel
Awards	<p>The first international awards for Accessible Tourism Destination (ATD2019) were awarded in 2020. This initiative was led by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the ONCE Foundation, for efforts by tourist destinations to be accessible to all. Barcelona was honoured with the award for the best urban destination in the inaugural Accessible Tourism Destination competition. The roots of Barcelona's accessibility date back to 1992 when the city hosted the Olympic Games. It marked the first time that the Olympic and Paralympic Games were integrated and given equal status. Consequently, all Olympic facilities were designed to the highest accessibility standards. The entire city underwent a significant transformation, shaping its future urban layout with accessibility as paramount consideration. Since 1992, there has been a unified policy by the Barcelona City Council and all its departments, particularly the Municipal Institute for Persons with Disabilities, along with the private and service sectors, aimed at building a more accessible city. The road system is designed with accessibility in mind, featuring a comprehensive network of ramps and sidewalks for the visually impaired, and pedestrian crossings with auditory signals. Public facilities, including hotels, meet accessibility standards, ensuring they can be visited by everyone, regardless of physical, sensory, or cognitive abilities.</p> <p>Barcelona was awarded third prize in the Access City Award (granted by the European Commission) in 2022. This award recognizes the city's adaptation for people with special needs. The justification also highlighted the accessibility of hotels.</p>
Information about the building	<p>Mercer Hotel in Barcelona is a designated historical monument in the heart of Barcelona's Gothic Quarter. The building of the hotel incorporates segments of the Roman walls of ancient Barcino, some of which trace back to the 1st century A.D. Guests of the hotel are granted access to the medieval paintings adorning the 28th defence tower, encapsulating a unique blend of historical significance hospitality. The very essence of the Mercer Hotel Barcelona lies in its heritage, with its core elements fashioned from stone and its meticulous renovation overseen by the acclaimed</p>

	<p>architect Rafael Moneo, recipient of the prestigious Prince of Asturias prize in 2012. Encircled by 17th-century columns, the medieval courtyard is graced by three venerable orange trees, imparting a refreshing ambiance. Archways, balconies, and expansive windows, modified and added over the centuries, provide an idyllic setting.</p>
<p>Information about accessibility solutions</p>	<p>The Mercer Hotel offers public spaces and specially adapted guest rooms, which are in full compliance with the American Disabilities Act. The Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) sets forth requirements for hotels and other places of public accommodation to ensure accessibility for individuals with disabilities. Some key provisions of the ADA pertaining to hotels include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible Accommodations: Hotels must provide accessible guest rooms and suites that comply with ADA standards. These rooms should feature amenities such as widened doorways, accessible bathrooms with grab bars and roll-in showers or accessible bathtubs, visual alarms, and other accessibility features as required. • Public Spaces Accessibility: Hotels must ensure that public areas such as lobbies, restaurants, lounges, fitness centres, swimming pools, and meeting rooms are accessible to individuals with disabilities. This includes features like accessible entrances, pathways, seating, and other accommodations to facilitate access for people with mobility impairments. • Reservation Policies: Hotels are required to provide accessible rooms to individuals with disabilities upon request, and they cannot discriminate against guests with disabilities in their reservation policies or room assignment practices. • Communication Accessibility: Hotels must ensure effective communication with individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing by providing auxiliary aids and services such as TTY phones, captioned televisions, and assistive listening devices upon request. • Service Animals: Hotels must allow individuals with disabilities to be accompanied by their service animals in all areas of the hotel where guests are normally allowed, with certain limited exceptions. • Renovation and Alteration Requirements: When hotels undergo renovations or alterations, they must make changes to improve accessibility to the extent feasible, in accordance with ADA standards. • ADA Compliance Documentation: Hotels are required to maintain documentation of their compliance with ADA accessibility requirements, including records of accessibility features, policies, and procedures. <p>Overall, the ADA aims to ensure that individuals with disabilities have equal access to the goods, services, and accommodations offered by hotels and other places of public accommodation, thereby promoting inclusivity and equal opportunity for all.</p>
<p>Photos & sources https://www.mercerbarcelona.com/en</p>	

Barcelona, Spain. Cale de Ramon Turro, 196-198, 08005	
Building function/typology	lunion Hotel
Awards: Universal Accessibility Certification	The hotel is certified to ensure that facilities offer universal accessibility, providing a series of technical aids and staff have been trained to help users with all needs.
Information about the building	The building is in the Poblenou district, with old factories, and the production district near the sea. Building has 224 rooms, 11 meetings rooms, private car park, pool on the roof, fitness center and restaurant.
Information about accessibility solutions	<p>Entrance and floors don't have any thresholds and all the facilities are on one level. In the building is a lift which is designed in multisensory way and gives opportunities to fit requirements of all the guests (braille descriptions, bumped, big font numbers, voice description). On the terrace is placed the swimming pool which is accessible for people with disabilities because of the slope and an added special lift to the water. Lift also fits all the levels (including the terrace which is not so common in other hotels). Hotel offers the accessible rooms in which it is possible to find facilities for wheelchairs users and visually impaired people. All the public and shared spaces are accessible. The building is located near an accessible beach.</p> <p>The building is listed on tourist websites recommending places accessible to people with disabilities, for example: https://www.tur4all.com/resources/380</p> <p>Below pictures describe hotel at that webpage:</p> <p>The accessible report is available here: https://www.tur4all.com/resources/hotel-casa-fuster-h-gl/user/report/pdf</p>
Photos & sources	

5.2 Educational buildings, Italy

PADOVA, ITALY Via VIII Febbraio, 2, 35122	
Building function/typology	BO PALACE and its adjacent university buildings, UNIVERSITY OF PADUA
Award	In 2016, The Gattamelata Award for Institutions was awarded to the University of Padua stating, "The 2016 Gattamelata Prize was awarded to the University of Padua for its commitment to promote an active inclusion process that reaches beyond the

	general concept of integration, made possible through the involvement of both internal and external participants.”	
Information about the building	The Palazzo del Bo in Padua is a fifteenth-century complex and the historic seat of the University of Padua, one of the oldest universities in the world. It is still home to the Rectorate and the School of Law. It is also home to the oldest anatomical theatre in the world.	
Information about accessibility solutions	The University of Padua is very concerned about inclusiveness (https://www.unipd.it/en/home/inclusive-university ; https://www.facebook.com/universitapadovainclusiva) at the same time it is difficult to find information about the suitability of university buildings for people with disabilities. The photos of the historic Palazzo Bo building show at least some adaptation for people with disabilities.	
Photos & sources		
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bo_Palace#/media/File:Palazzo_Bo_(Padua).jpg https://www.google.com/maps/@45.4066076,11.8772281,3a,90y,291.65h,72.86t/data=!3m6!1e1!3m4!1sRDRU1nGciR9FXvGu3uk0Ww!2e0!7i13312!8i6656?entry=ttu https://www.google.com/maps/@45.4067623,11.877183,2a,90y,236.86h,86.21t/data=!3m6!1e1!3m4!1svvvRXuEEY9Dakwc7sFWcg!2e0!7i13312!8i6656?entry=ttu		

FIRENZE/FLORENCE, ITALY Via della Mattonaia, 8 - 50121	
Building function/typology	THE EX-CONVENT OF SANTA VERDIANA, Università degli Studi di Firenze UNIFI - University of Florence
Awards	<p>Florence received a special mention in the ACCESS CITY AWARD 2021. From the award report: “In modern cities, it can be relatively simple to make new developments accessible. However, it is more challenging to adapt to existing environments, particularly in historic cities with ancient, monumental buildings and narrow, cobbled streets.</p> <p>Despite facing these challenges, Florence has made exceptional progress. It has done so by following an ambitious Adaptation Plan for Buildings and Public Spaces, which it updates each year. The plan covers aspects ranging from roads, pavements and car</p>

	<p>parks to gardens, sports facilities, libraries, and museums. Based on this, Florence has renovated 29 public facilities, including schools, sports centers, and libraries, to make them more accessible. In 2019, the city appointed a Disability Manager to promote the needs of persons with disabilities in its development. The Disability Manager coordinates accessibility-related actions, working closely with city departments and associations.”</p>
<p>Information about the building</p>	<p>The new headquarters of the Department of Architecture of the University of Florence has been established within the historical complex of Santa Verdiana, which included part of a former convent and spaces once used as a female prison. Located on the outskirts of the Santa Croce district, the complex of the former convent of Santa Verdiana occupies a portion of the block between Piazza Ghiberti, Via dell'Agnolo, and Via Ferdinando Paolieri. Acquired in 1986 by the University of Florence, in the following years it underwent radical restoration and adaptation interventions aimed at improving its functional aspect and restoring spaces and volumes of historical and architectural value compromised by its long use as a prison. It is precisely this blend of open and exchange spaces (the bustling sphere of life and negotiations typical of the market), meditative places (the convent), and restrictive spaces (the prison) that is one of the most valuable elements. Currently, it hosts the master’s degree courses in Architecture, the five-year single-cycle degree program, the bachelor’s degree Program in Landscape Architecture, and the master’s Program in Architectural Design.</p>
<p>Information about accessibility solutions</p>	<p>The University of Florence has been active for many years to offer students with disabilities equal opportunities in their right to education, by implementing specific actions to remove obstacles limiting their integration into the university world. The Department of Architecture has established the Florence Accessibility Lab Interdepartmental Research Unit, set up with the intention of defining, consolidating and promoting a new culture of accessibility, as a collective resource for autonomy of people and social inclusion, to make local communities more vital, safe and cohesive, for the valorization - also for tourism purposes - of the architectural and landscape heritage, and for the development of advanced technologies at the service of the individual.</p> <p>“The ADA Project. Home Adaptation for the Autonomy of severe disabled people”. conducted by the lab was selected by the Jury of DESIGN FOR ALL FOUNDATION in the 2018 edition of the Awards as a Winer in spaces, products, and services already in use category.</p> <p>Building: The recent modernization and revitalization were carried out in accordance with building regulations ensuring accessibility but as a historic monument building can’t be fully accessible. The new building and the new entrance were designed. The new access was created as part of a redevelopment project in Largo Annigoni following an agreement between the Municipality of Florence, the University of Florence and Firenze Parcheggi. The new opening through Firenze Parcheggi's premises connects Largo Annigoni with the internal courtyard of Santa Verdiana, which has been redeveloped and now houses the new porter's lodge, for reception and entrance control, and a new emergency staircase and access to the upper floors. The lighting, signage and paving of the courtyard have also been renewed. "In addition to being more functional for the flow of students," commented Rector Alessandra Petrucci, "the new entrance represents a link between the heart of the district and the history of the former convent, which opens up even more to the city".</p>

5.3 Offices, Estonia

HAAPSALU CITY, ESTONIA	
Building function/typology	<p>Chosen office space in old, heritage buildings but not fully accessible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Haapsalu Vabakontor, Karja 27, 90502, Haapsalu
Awards	EDEN – European award for accessible and sustainable tourism, 2013
Information about the town and accessibility solutions	<p>The 700-year-old seaside town of Haapsalu is situated on the West Coast of Estonia and has been called the Venice of the north. The town is 100 kilometres away from Tallinn and is reputed for its historic, maritime ambiance, warm sea water, curative mud baths and friendly residents.</p> <p>Accessibility: As a spa town and a city with a specialized school and care centre, Haapsalu has a long history of hosting people with disabilities. Local government and businesses are dedicated to improving accessibility in town. The Läänemaa Chamber of Disabled People is a local umbrella organization that brings together disabled peoples' groups from across the country and regularly discusses accessibility issues.</p>
Information about accessibility solutions in office buildings	<p>Creating an accessible office design is crucial for accommodating individuals with disabilities and ensuring inclusivity in the workplace. Here are some features of accessible office design:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Entrance and Exits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide, unobstructed entrances/exits with automatic doors. • Ramps or elevators for individuals with mobility impairments. • Clearly marked accessible routes from parking areas and public transportation stops. 2. Interior Layout:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide hallways and corridors to accommodate wheelchair users and individuals with mobility aids. • Clear signage with large, easy-to-read fonts and Braille for visually impaired individuals. • Open floor plans to allow for easy navigation and movement. 3. Workstations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Height-adjustable desks to accommodate individuals who use wheelchairs or have different ergonomic needs. • Adjustable chairs with lumbar support and armrests. • Accessible power outlets and charging stations at reachable heights. • Desks with adequate knee space for wheelchair users. 4. Restrooms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible restrooms equipped with grab bars, lower sinks, and toilets with adequate space for manoeuvrability. • Clear signage indicating the location of accessible restrooms. • Automatic faucets, soap dispensers, and hand dryers for ease of use. 5. Lighting and Acoustics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even lighting throughout the office space to reduce glare and accommodate individuals with visual impairments. • Acoustic treatments minimize noise and create a comfortable environment for individuals with hearing impairments. 6. Technology and Equipment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes screen readers, magnifiers, and voice recognition software for individuals with visual or motor impairments. • Ergonomic keyboards, mice, and other input devices to accommodate individuals with mobility issues. • Adjustable monitor arms to accommodate different viewing angles and heights. 7. Meeting Rooms and Common Areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible meeting rooms with adjustable tables and seating arrangements to accommodate individuals with various needs. • Accessible teleconference and video conference equipment for remote participants. • Quiet rooms or designated spaces for individuals who need privacy or sensory accommodations. 8. Emergency Evacuation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evacuation routes and procedures that consider individuals with disabilities. • Accessible evacuation chairs or other equipment for safely evacuating individuals with mobility impairments. • Emergency communication systems that are accessible to individuals with hearing or visual impairments. 9. Training and Awareness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee training programs to raise awareness about accessibility issues and best practices. • Regular accessibility audits to identify and address any barriers or deficiencies in the workplace design. • Inclusion of accessibility considerations in the office design and renovation process from the outset.
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	By incorporating these features into office design, organizations can create an inclusive and welcoming environment for all employees, regardless of their abilities or disabilities.
<p>Photos & sources – chosen buildings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Haapsalu Vabakontor <p>https://vabakontor.ee/en/start/</p>	

5.4 Residential Building/Collective Housing Building, Portugal

PORTO, PORTUGAL	
Building function/typology	Collective housing building, Pousada do Porto - Rua das Flores
Awards	The UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) has presented Portugal with the Accessible Tourist Destination 2019 award. The entire old center with some old historic buildings has been placed on the World Heritage List of UNESCO and Porto was part of the list of nominated cities for the City Access Award 2022.
Information about the building	<p>Pousada do Porto - Rua das Flores epitomizes an architectural gem within Porto's historic enclave, meticulously refurbished from an 18th-century edifice situated on a pedestrian-only thoroughfare. This boutique luxury hotel, boasting 84 rooms, represents a harmonious blend of historical preservation and modern sophistication.</p> <p>While the architectural integrity of the 18th-century structure remains meticulously conserved, Pestana's design team has embraced a contemporary aesthetic, eschewing the replication of interior styles prevalent in the 1700s. Adorned with stone walls and herringbone floors, the ambiance exudes timeless elegance. However, the furnishings and decor exude a distinctly contemporary flair, characterized by vibrant hues and subtle floral motifs paying homage to the renowned Rua das Flores.</p>
Information about accessibility solutions	<p>Facilities for disabled guests, Family rooms Lift, Soundproof rooms, Wheelchair accessible, Emergency cord in bathroom, 24-hour security, Smoke alarms</p> <p>ACCESSIBLE ROOMS:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider Doorways: The doorways are wide enough to accommodate a wheelchair. • Low Thresholds: Thresholds are kept low or eliminated to allow easy entry and exit for wheelchair users. • Accessible Bathroom: The bathroom is designed to be spacious and equipped with features such as roll-in showers, grab bars, shower benches, and handheld showerheads. The toilet may have grab bars and be of a higher height for easier transfer from the wheelchair. • Accessible Sink and Countertops: The sink and countertops are lowered to a suitable height for wheelchair users, allowing them to reach the amenities comfortably. • Accessible Furniture Arrangement: Furniture in the room is arranged to provide ample manoeuvring space for wheelchair users. • Elevator.
<p>Photos & sources</p> <p>https://www.tripadvisor.com/Hotel_Review-g189180-d23512224-Reviews-Pousada_do_Porto_Rua_das_Flores-Porto_Porto_District_Northern_Portugal.html</p>	

5.5 Museum, Poland

Warsaw, Poland, Rynek Starego Miasta 28/42, 00 – 272 Warszawa	
Building Typology	Museum
Awards Accessibility Lider 2019	In the category historic listed building for the best investment in modernization of the building in the context of needs of the users with disabilities. (https://www.prezydent.pl/aktualnosci/wydarzenia/iv-edycji-konkursu-architektoniczno-urbanistycznego-lider-dostepnosci-2019,1371)

Information about the building	The museum is part of 11 historic, listed townhouses on the Warsaw Old Town part. Most of the buildings were destroyed during the Second World War and were reconstructed to reflect the originals.
Information about accessibility solutions	During the renovation of the Museum of Warsaw sources, special and functional plans of the building increased the buildings' accessibility. Although it is not fully accessible, many solutions allow people with different types of disabilities to take part in most of the activities.
Photos and Sources	

5.6 Rest house, Poland

Koscielisko, Kiry 36, Koscielisko, Poland	
Building function/typology	House Of Creative Work and Rest „Wrzos” (Dom Pracy Twórczej i Wypoczynku „Wrzos”)
Awards Accessibility was done as a part of a grant from PFRON (Polish State Fund for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled).	Increasing accessibility of this historic building was a part of a grant project entitled “Adaptation of the utility building with technical infrastructure and building facilities in Kościelisko, Kiry 36 Street to the needs of people with disabilities”. The project is co-financed with funds from PFRON. In 2022 University of Warsaw signed an agreement with the State Fund for Rehabilitation of People with Disabilities as a part of the pilot program “Accessibility beyond barriers”.
Information about the building	The House of Creative Work and Rest “Wrzos” has been owned by the University of Warsaw (Poland) since 1973. A historical building with timber

	<p>structure of Zakopiański style common for this region of Poland. Near the building is the entrance to the Tatra National Park and Kościeliska Valley, which is mostly accessible for people on wheelchairs and children in strollers.</p>
<p>Information about accessibility solutions</p>	<p>Entrance and floors don't have thresholds. One entrance is available for everyone after addition of a metal ramp. In the building two rooms for people with disabilities are available. The bathroom has all facilities necessary for wheelchair users. There are 13 rooms for a maximum of 28 people. Of these, 11 rooms are accessible for visually impaired people and other disabilities in which a wheelchair is not needed. In some rooms massaging mattresses were added. There is also a kitchen, dining room and meeting place which are accessible via lift. The purchase of a portable hearing-assist induction loop is planned. Braille signage is planned at the facility, as well as a tactile map presenting the tourist attractions of the Polish Tatra Mountains. Equipment will be supplemented with an outdoor gym adapted to the needs of people with disabilities. In addition, the house will have a two-seater electric scooter, a tricycle (including a tandem) with electric assistance, trekking bikes and electric bicycles to allow organization of independent trips.</p>
<p>Photos & sources https://bssoc.uw.edu.pl/dom-pracy-tworczej-i-wypoczynku-wrzos-w-koscielisku/</p>	

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has shown the specific climate, comfort, and energy considerations for heritage buildings in Europe and how they differ from contemporary building renovation requirements. Special attention is given to the building typologies studied in the Herit4ages project (offices, classrooms, residential buildings, hotels). Different energy profiles exist for historic and traditional heritage buildings, which vary according to the year of construction due to the materials used, especially those built in periods before the 1960s. An appropriate energy renovation strategy must improve the buildings' performance in terms of energy and comfort, while adapting its use to meet contemporary expectations. Building renovation is also favourable for local economies, as it would revitalize

tourism activity in historical urban neighbourhoods. Regarding building renovation in the EU, several directives and standards at European level and regulations at local level have been developed to address the specific needs of historic building renovation to improve energy and comfort. However, local regulations usually impose rigorous limitations that are established from a heritage preservation point of view, which limit the type of interventions allowed to be performed in historic buildings, translating to a specific set of renovation technologies.

However, the implementation of strategies to achieve energy efficiency in existing buildings already represents a complex process, due to energy and comfort goals which frequently oppose each other. When the renovation involves a building with an architectural value that must be preserved due to its historic or cultural legacy, the complexity increases since new dimensions are added to the decision-making criteria. Decision-making processes and tools such as EN 16883 are recommended to select the most adequate solution for every case, as well as considering an evaluation of the potential solutions according to their energy and comfort impact and feasibility of installation.

In this deliverable it was also analysed the implications that climate, user profiles and occupancy have on the design of the renovation strategy to be applied in each case, and the goals to be set for thermal comfort by considering such conditions. Several technologies exist to accomplish the energy efficiency and thermal comfort goal that also meet the requirements of heritage preservation regulations. However, they present both advantages and disadvantages, since they can modify the existing balances between thermal inertia, relative humidity and ventilation. Thorough energy studies are required and possibly more extensive works needed in order to avoid drastic and negative changes.

This study has introduced the importance of accessibility and universal design in the renovation of historic and heritage buildings, since it was not an objective generally considered at the time of their creation. However, the review of heritage buildings with good practice interventions for accessibility represents the series of actions required to meet new usage expectations for different kinds of users.

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